

The Primordial Coupling Constant Function, Fermion Imperfect Rings and Poincare Tensions – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the framework of the 8-theory and in particular the coupling constant Equation in pi representation, it is possible to correlate the invariant (3) to Poincare tensions, i.e. interactions between the electron and the nuclei which lead to imperfect ring and to the electron to divert from the pi value. Such relationship between the electron and the nuclei have been proven accurate in quantum mechanics.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{0}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N(V)_V + (3) \right) + N(V)_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1}$$

$$N(V)_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{2}$$

$$N(V)_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N(V)_V = P_{max} \text{ in Range } [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{i=1}^{i=R} N(V)_V + (3) \right) + N(V)_V \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{i=1}^{i=R} N(V)_V + (\pi) \right) + N(V)_V \tag{3}$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3} \right) : (24 + (\pi)) + 3 : (120 + (\pi)) + 5 : (840 + (\pi)) + 7 ... \tag{4}$$

$$8 + \left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) : (24 + (\pi)) + \pi : (120 + (\pi)) + (\pi + 1.82) : (840 + (\pi)) + (2\pi + 0.716) \dots \quad (5)$$

We saw that this representation of the coupling constant equation is indicating that the electron is cyclic, but not a perfect cycle as it is not pi. Reader is assumed to read the thesis and to be familiar with how the equation was derived. So we can attribute the variation of three from pi, to the Poincare tension between the electron and the nuclei. That makes sense since:

$$3 < (\pi) \quad (6)$$

$$3 \rightarrow \pi \quad (7)$$

This of course could come with an agreement with the pull of the nuclei on the electron. It does not have to be the electron, we only analyze the coupling constant equation third element has it is the most familiar. It can also be analyzed in a different fashion, in the context of vibration. The electron is not a perfect circle but a vibrating and varying entity, such features causing the representation a slight diversion from pi.

Up to this date, the coupling constant equation has several meanings. The first was in the context of variations. The second, in the context of spin, the third in the context of the arrow, the fourth was in the context of pi, areas of propagation and the two possible meaning of the pi. The idea in this paper is not a proof of any sort, just an educated guess regarding the relation of three and pi in the 8-theory.

A very interesting question remain. Can a number of dimension in our distinct manifold be represented within the coupling constant equation. The fact that are only three spatial dimensions and the interesting fact of the invariant three, could mean that the boson can be propagated only in three dimensions, its just a speculation for now, but proving such a thing would be an astonishing achievement.

Pi and the invariant (3) are very important significant. We found the spin representation:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (8)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (9)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (10)$$

Is there a dimensional representation as well?

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)